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Abstract:

This document presents the final report of WP5.2 (Open Science and Data) within the EURO-LABS project. The work package aimed to promote Open Science and FAIR data management practices across the European accelerator-based science community by developing shared services, governance structures, and training activities. Together, these activities have strengthened the adoption of Open Science principles within the EURO-LABS community and established sustainable foundations for future collaboration, data sharing, and integration with European Open Science initiatives, including the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

EURO-LABS Consortium, 2026

For more information on EURO-LABS, its partners and contributors please see <https://web.infn.it/EURO-LABS/>

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Executive summary

WP5.2 has established the foundations of a sustainable Open Science ecosystem for the EURO-LABS community by delivering interoperable services, governance structures, and training activities supporting FAIR data management and reproducible research practices across European accelerator-based science facilities.

A major achievement of the work package is the development and deployment of the openNP catalogue, a FAIR-compliant metadata repository designed to improve the findability, accessibility, and reuse of nuclear physics datasets. Based on community standards and persistent identifiers, the platform enables the integration of datasets, software, and scientific publications within a common framework, thereby strengthening reproducibility and facilitating data sharing across Research Infrastructures.

Complementary digital services were also deployed to support collaborative research activities. In particular, a federated Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) based on INDIGO IAM was established, providing secure and scalable access to scientific services through institutional credentials, ORCID identities, and EURO-LABS accounts. The infrastructure is now used by several production services, including the openNP catalogue, the THEO4EXP platform, and the FRS data access and monitoring services at GSI, demonstrating its value as a common building block for the EURO-LABS digital ecosystem.

To ensure the long-term sustainability of these developments, a governance framework involving participating Research Infrastructures, service operators, and data curators was established. Dedicated Governing and Curator Boards were created to oversee the future evolution of the openNP catalogue, while participating institutions are committed to maintaining the operational services beyond the duration of the project.

In parallel, two international training schools, sponsored by EURO-LABS and within the framework of the advanced training program, were organised to promote FAIR data management, Open Science practices, collaborative software development, and reproducible research methodologies. These events provided hands-on training to early-career researchers and contributed to the development of a growing community of Open Science practitioners within accelerator-based sciences.

Together, these achievements have strengthened the adoption of Open Science practices across the EURO-LABS community and established sustainable foundations for future collaboration, data sharing, and integration with broader European initiatives, including the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

1. INTRODUCTION

Open Science has become a central pillar of European research policy, promoting transparency, reproducibility, accessibility and reuse of scientific outputs. Within accelerator-based sciences, experimental data are often distributed across multiple facilities, collaborations and national infrastructures, creating challenges for findability and long-term preservation.

WP5.2 addressed these challenges by developing common tools, services and training activities supporting FAIR data management and Open Science practices across the EURO-LABS research infrastructures. The activities focused on three complementary pillars: (i) development of the openNP metadata catalogue, (ii) deployment of shared authentication and access services, and (iii) training and community building. This report summarises the achievements, impact and sustainability plans resulting from these activities.

2. THE OPENNP CATALOGUE

2.1. DESCRIPTION

Within EURO-LABS WP5.2, significant progress has been made towards establishing a common framework for FAIR and Open Science data management in the nuclear physics community. A major outcome is the development and release of the openNP catalogue in August 2025 [1-2], a metadata repository designed to improve the discoverability, accessibility and reusability of nuclear physics datasets across European Research Infrastructures (RIs).

2.2. USE

The primary objective of openNP is to provide a centralized metadata-only catalogue for nuclear physics datasets. The platform supports FAIR principles by enabling standardized metadata registration, persistent identification of datasets, and improved findability through a common web portal. It is designed to serve experimental, simulated and processed datasets and to accommodate both generic and nuclear-physics-specific metadata, such as beam characteristics, experimental setups, targets, facilities, software and analysis workflows.

Following an initial evaluation of data repository solutions described in Milestone Report MS35 [3], we adopted the InvenioRDM framework [4] as the technical foundation of the catalogue. This choice provided a flexible and extensible metadata model aligned with DataCite [5] (DOI provider) standards along with advanced search capabilities, and FAIR data management practices.

The project also established the organization model for the records of the catalogue. Using the InvenioRDM features, datasets can be grouped and curated within dedicated RI communities, with identified roles for managers, curators and contributors. This structure provides a scalable mechanism for dataset submission, review and publication while supporting future expansion to additional laboratories and detector collaborations.

Using a GANIL use-case dataset, the catalogue successfully demonstrated its capability to integrate multiple related research outputs, including raw experimental data, processed datasets and analysis software, each identified through persistent DOIs. By exploiting DataCite relations between records, openNP demonstrated its ability to be FAIR-compliant and connect datasets, software and publications into a coherent research ecosystem, illustrating the added value of the catalogue for

scientific reproducibility and data reuse.

2.3. GOVERNANCE AND POLICIES

After the Fourth Annual Meeting of EURO-LABS in October 2025, a governance framework has been established to ensure the sustainability, quality assurance and alignment of openNP with the needs of the EURO-LABS RIs.

A Governing Board consisting of 5 members among GANIL, GSI, CNA, INFN and LPCCaen has been established. It is responsible for ensuring the strategic oversight of the catalogue (alignment with FAIR data principles, priorities for future development) and endorsing data curators members. After a first call to action, data curators and data management practices have been identified among the interested RIs, including CNA, DACM, GSI, INFN-LNL, INFN-LNF, RAPIN-INCT and TRIGA, forming the Curator Board.

These two boards will continue the governance of the OpenNP service beyond the EURO-LABS project.

2.4. LONG-TERM SUPPORT AND OUTLOOK

The platform was deployed on the CC-IN2P3 Kubernetes [7-8] cloud infrastructure using container orchestration and continuous integration/deployment workflows, ensuring long-term sustainability and scalability.

After the first deployment, further developments have been initiated to support the long-term evolution of the service. These activities include the customization of metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies for nuclear physics, participation in the NAPMIX project [9] for cross-domain metadata standards, development of automated dataset import, preparation of governance and curation policies, and plans for broader adoption across EURO-LABS facilities and collaborations.

In this direction, the most recent developments of openNP introduced InvenioRDM (v13+) “Collection” and “Subcommunity” new features [10], enabling the aggregation of heterogeneous datasets under a single experiment number. The indexing of records at the experiment level, combined with the hierarchical collaborations model now allow more efficient discovery services with openNP. This facilitates the reconstruction of complete experimental workflows, strengthening FAIR compliance, reproducibility and data reuse across the EURO-LABS community.

3. SERVICES AND PROTOTYPES

3.1. IAM AUTHENTICATION

3.1.1. Description

A core service for sharing data is authentication and authorization. As part of the EURO-LABS project, such a service has been deployed, based on the OpenID Connect (OIDC) and OAuth2 protocols which are the mainstream standards for authentication and authorization, in particular but

not only for web applications. A nice feature of IOC/OAuth2 is that it can be used also with command line tools that are significantly present in the community.

The service has been deployed using the INDIGO IAM product [11], an open source implementation of an OIDC/Oauth2 provider, developed in the context of the INDIGO DataCloud project (2015-2017) and since then adopted by many large scientific communities, in particular the CERN/LHC experiments. The service is hosted and operated by IJCLab, a French partner of the project with a strong experience in distributed computing and in particular in authentication/authorization technologies.

Started in 2023, it allows users to use their home institute credentials, through eduGAIN federation [12], rather than having not well managed specific credentials. Even if most laboratories and institutes in the community are connected to eduGAIN, some of them have difficulties using it. For this reason, ORCID was added as another way to authenticate with EURO-LABS. For some specific use cases, it is also possible to create a EURO-LABS specific account. With INDIGO IAM, a user can have several identities (i.e., source of authentication) but still be the same users for applications, a key feature in our context where a user can be a member or have an account at several institutions.

A few EURO-LABS applications relying on INDIGO IAM to authenticate users and to authorize access are described below. Application integration has proven to be easy as OIDC/OAuth is a standard supported by almost all application frameworks.

EURO-LABS INDIGO IAM instance has 500 registered users. The service has been very reliable since the beginning and IJCLab experts provided very good support to help using the service efficiently.

3.1.2. Use cases

openNP Catalogue

The openNP catalogue is one of the primary services relying on the EURO-LABS IAM infrastructure. As a FAIR-compliant metadata catalogue for nuclear physics datasets, openNP supports different user roles including administrators, community managers, curators, and contributors. The authentication and authorization requirements therefore extend beyond simple user login and require fine-grained access control for record submission, review, publication, and community management.

By integrating with the EURO-LABS INDIGO IAM service through OpenID Connect, openNP provides a secure and user-friendly authentication mechanism allowing researchers to access the platform using their institutional credentials via eduGAIN, ORCID accounts, or dedicated EURO-LABS identities. This approach avoids the creation of local user databases and ensures consistent identity management across participating Research Infrastructures.

The IAM integration also facilitates the implementation of community-based governance within openNP. User roles and permissions can be managed centrally and assigned according to the governance structure established for the catalogue, supporting the activities of community managers

and data curators while maintaining traceability and accountability of user actions. The successful deployment of openNP demonstrates the ability of the EURO-LABS IAM infrastructure to support complex scientific services requiring both authentication and authorization capabilities.

Theo4Exp Service

Another successful integration of the EURO-LABS INDIGO IAM service is the Theo4Exp platform [14], a web-based service developed within EURO-LABS to facilitate interactions between experimentalists and theorists and to support the preparation and interpretation of accelerator-based experiments. The service provides access to theoretical models, simulation tools, and community resources through a common web portal.

The integration of Theo4Exp with the EURO-LABS IAM infrastructure enabled users to authenticate using their institutional credentials through the eduGAIN federation, ORCID accounts, or dedicated EURO-LABS accounts when required. By relying on OpenID Connect standards, the integration was achieved with minimal development effort while ensuring compatibility with the broader EURO-LABS authentication ecosystem.

This deployment demonstrated the ability of the IAM service to support community-facing scientific applications and provided users with a seamless single sign-on experience across EURO-LABS services. The integration also simplified user management for service operators by delegating authentication and identity management to a trusted central infrastructure.

FRS Experimental Data Server (GSI)

INDIGO IAM was used to provide authentication and authorization for the public data server of the Fragment Separator (FRS) collaboration at GSI. The service replaced a legacy authentication mechanism based on HTTP Basic Authentication and shared experiment-specific usernames and passwords distributed through experiment spokespersons. This approach presented limitations in terms of security, traceability, and user management.

The migration to the EURO-LABS IAM infrastructure was straightforward thanks to the adoption of the OpenID Connect standard and the use of the Apache module `mod_auth_oidc`. Individual user identities are now managed centrally, while access to experiment-specific resources is controlled through IAM groups. Researchers can request membership to the appropriate experimental groups, allowing access rights to be granted and revoked in a transparent and auditable manner.

Beyond improved security and compliance with modern authentication practices, the deployment significantly reduced the administrative burden associated with account management. It also established a scalable framework that can be extended to additional experimental services and data repositories at GSI and other EURO-LABS facilities.

3.1.3. Governance and long term support

The service deployed within the EURO-LABS framework is a foundational component that serves as a core platform for the deployment of services across the entire community. IJCLab has committed to continuing to operate the instance and provide support on a best-effort basis after the end of the project, as it is operating several other INDIGO IAM instances for other national and international projects.

3.2. REMOTE ACCESS TO EXPERIMENTAL METADATA AT THE FRS AT GSI

To improve access to experimental metadata generated by the Fragment Separator (FRS) facility at GSI, including electronic logbooks, simulation outputs, run sheets, and related documentation, a dedicated data service infrastructure was deployed in collaboration with the GSI IT department. The service provides a centralised platform for the storage and dissemination of experiment-related information, facilitating collaboration between researchers located both on-site and at external institutions.

The infrastructure is accessible from within and outside the GSI network and includes 1 TB of shared Network File System (NFS) storage available from Linux and Windows systems connected to the GSI computing environment. External access is provided through an Apache HTTP server integrated with the EURO-LABS INDIGO IAM authentication service. Access rights are managed through user groups and permissions, ensuring secure and controlled access to experiment-specific resources while avoiding the use of shared credentials.

In addition to static data access, the platform supports a collection of dynamic services dedicated to remote experiment monitoring. These services, collectively referred to as the *Virtual Messhütte*—named after the FRS experimental counting room—provide researchers with real-time information on the status and performance of ongoing experiments. A suite of Python-based applications gathers and publishes monitoring information from internal GSI services, enabling collaborators to follow experimental activities remotely and participate more effectively in data-taking campaigns.

To support long-term monitoring and analysis, the infrastructure also hosts a Grafana and Graphite-based time-series database. This service provides visualisation, monitoring, and archival capabilities for operational and experimental parameters, with a planned data retention period of ten years. Together, these services enhance the accessibility, transparency, and long-term preservation of experimental metadata, supporting collaborative research and contributing to the broader Open Science objectives of EURO-LABS.

4. TRAINING

4.1. FIRST DATA SCHOOL (GSI)

As part of the advanced training program planned by EURO-LABS, from 24th to 27th of November 2024, an advanced training course on Open Science and Data Management took place at Castle Eberburg in the German region of Rhineland-Palatinate [15]. The training brought together a diverse group of early-careers researchers, ranging from final year master's students to postdoctoral researchers. In addition, the school attracted young Open Science professionals, such as data managers. A total of 18 researchers together with 11 tutors attended the school representing institutions in France, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Romania, Spain and Switzerland.

The training aimed to develop skills and knowledge on Open Science principles, including Open data and software, workflows and tools. In addition, emphasis was put on data and software management best practices to employ throughout the lifecycle of a research project. The lectures were designed to drive the uptake in Open Science and good data management practices, and to encourage the participants to act as Open Science ambassadors for their research communities.

A core element of the school was the Hands-On Data Challenge, which took place on every day of the course during the week. Participants applied the methodologies introduced earlier in the course. A succinct analysis of a γ -ray spectroscopy dataset served as the basis for these exercises. These sessions provided participants with practical experience in implementing data management practices. Working with two differing experimental datasets, they developed important data management skills and gained hands-on experience with relevant software in a collaborative setting. Participants created data management plans, utilized software version control, and generated metadata, demonstrating the importance and benefits of robust data management for enhancing scientific practices. The work was carried out in teams, with team members selected to obtain balanced skill sets across the groups. The groups were requested to share their results between their datasets to improve the scientific outputs through interoperability. The exercise served as a useful learning experience of working together in a collaborative environment. The results and experiences from the data challenge were shared by each group at the end of the week.

A survey was held at the end of the school, were completed by 16 participants. Overall, the feedback from the participants was very positive, in numbers on average the school was graded with 4.4 out of 5 points.

4.2. SECOND DATA SCHOOL (GANIL)

As part of the advanced training program planned by EURO-LABS, the second Advanced Training School, focused on “collaborative software development practices”, was held at GANIL from 2nd to 6th of February 2026 [16]. This event gathered 19 participants, including Master's and Ph.D. students as well as postdocs, from Spain, Japan, Sweden, Portugal, Belgium and France, alongside with 7 tutors.

Building on the success of the first edition, this edition aimed to promote modern software best practices and Open Science to enable effective data management and collaborative software development in a research context.

The school combined theoretical lectures with practical, team-based sessions including a hands-on data challenge. The lectures covered essential tools for collaborative workflows and reproducible research environments, such as software version control with GitLab and workflow automation with Snakemake. Particular emphasis was placed on effective data management practices for reproducible experimental analysis, including FAIR principles, Data Management Plans, and metadata (standards, software, and automation).

A post-event survey, completed by 16 participants, revealed overall positive feedback, with 93% finding the content relevant to their expectations and all participants reporting that the school met their expectations. They appreciated the balance between lectures and hands-on sessions and expressed confidence in applying the tools and methods learned in their work. The methodologies introduced (collaborative software development, workflow automation, reproducibility, and FAIR principles) were considered “mostly useful” by 56% of participants, “highly useful and time-saving” by 38%, while 6% remained neutral. The hands-on data challenge was particularly well received, with 63% rating it as highly effective and 31% as mostly effective, while participants highlighted the value of collaborative problem-solving, the relevance of practical exercises, and the effective support from tutors, especially for challenges like Git branching practices.

Suggestions for future editions included allocating more time to metadata management, covering more advanced GitLab features, and adding a dedicated lecture on containers (Docker).

5. IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY

The activities carried out within WP5.2 have established the foundations of a sustainable Open Science ecosystem for the European accelerator-based science community. By combining technical developments, governance structures, and training activities, the work performed during EURO-LABS has contributed to improving the discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of scientific data across participating Research Infrastructures.

A major achievement of the work package is the deployment of the openNP catalogue, which provides a common entry point for the discovery of nuclear physics datasets and associated research outputs. Through the adoption of community standards based on DataCite metadata schemas, persistent identifiers, and FAIR data management principles, openNP enhances the visibility and reusability of research data produced within EURO-LABS facilities. The catalogue also demonstrates how datasets, software, and scientific publications can be connected through persistent metadata relationships, facilitating reproducible research and supporting cross-disciplinary collaborations.

The deployment of a federated Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure based on INDIGO IAM has further strengthened the Open Science ecosystem by enabling secure and user-friendly access to shared services. By relying on widely adopted standards and federated identities through

eduGAIN and ORCID, the service reduces barriers to collaboration between institutions while providing a scalable solution for future services and data-sharing platforms.

Beyond the technical developments, WP5.2 has contributed to building a culture of Open Science within the community. Two international training schools provided practical education on FAIR data management, reproducible research workflows, collaborative software development, and modern data analysis practices. These activities have helped equip a new generation of researchers with the skills required to implement Open Science principles in their daily work and to act as ambassadors within their respective institutions and collaborations.

Sustainability has been a central consideration throughout the project. The openNP catalogue is hosted on the CC-IN2P3 cloud infrastructure, ensuring reliable long-term operation and scalability. Governance structures, including a Governing Board and a Curator Board encompassing several EURO-LABS Research Infrastructures, have been established to oversee the future evolution of the service, coordinate curation activities, and maintain alignment with community requirements. Similarly, IJCLab has committed to continuing the operation and support of the INDIGO IAM service beyond the lifetime of EURO-LABS.

Together, these developments provide a sustainable framework for Open Science in accelerator-based sciences and position the EURO-LABS community to contribute effectively to broader European initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The services, expertise, and governance structures established during the project will continue to support FAIR data practices, reproducible research, and scientific collaboration well beyond the end of the EURO-LABS project.

6. CONCLUSIONS

WP5.2 successfully delivered a coherent set of tools, services, and community-building activities supporting the adoption of Open Science and FAIR data management practices within the EURO-LABS community. Through close collaboration between participating Research Infrastructures, the work package addressed key challenges related to the discoverability, accessibility, management, and reuse of scientific data generated by accelerator-based science facilities.

A major outcome of the project is the development and deployment of the openNP catalogue, which provides a sustainable and FAIR-compliant platform for the publication and discovery of nuclear physics datasets and associated research outputs. The catalogue demonstrates the feasibility of a common metadata framework across multiple infrastructures while promoting reproducibility and data reuse through the integration of datasets, software, and publications.

Complementing this effort, the deployment of a federated Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure based on INDIGO IAM established a robust foundation for secure access to data and services. The adoption of recognised standards and federated identities facilitates collaboration across institutions and lowers the barriers to the use of shared scientific services.

The work package also contributed significantly to community engagement and capacity building through two international training schools focused on Open Science, FAIR data management, reproducible research, and collaborative software development. These activities helped disseminate

best practices and foster a culture of openness among early-career researchers and technical staff across Europe.

Importantly, the sustainability of the outcomes has been addressed through the establishment of governance structures, long-term hosting commitments, and continued operational support by participating institutions. The Governing Board and Curator Board created during the project will ensure the continued evolution of the openNP catalogue, while the IAM infrastructure will remain available to support future community services.

Overall, WP5.2 has laid the foundations for a sustainable Open Science ecosystem in accelerator-based sciences. The services, expertise, and governance mechanisms established during EURO-LABS will continue to support FAIR data practices, reproducible research, and European scientific collaboration beyond the lifetime of the project, while contributing to broader initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IAM	Identity and Access Management
OIDC	OpenID Connect
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSO	Single Sign-On (authentication scheme)
WP	Work Package